

CUSTOMARY LAW ARBITRATION: THE ORIGIN - VALIDITY AND ENFORCEABILITY OF CUSTOMARY ARBITRAL AWARD BASED ON OATH TAKING IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The earliest and oldest method of settlement of disputes in Nigeria is by customary law arbitration mechanism. It is far older than the court system and could be said to be as old as the existence of human race on earth. It is based on the custom and tradition of the Nigerian people and is administered by the family head, kindred head, village heads, elders, chiefs, age grade groups, women leagues (“umu ada” in igbo land), priests of shrines, the traditional chiefs or ‘igwe’ in council, etc. Customary law arbitration has passed through a lot of challenges with effect that some jurists and scholars denied its existence. For example, Allot in his book *Essays in African Law*, denied the existence of customary law arbitration in Nigeria.¹ Uwaifo JCA in *Okporuwu v. Okpokam*² stated that there is nothing like customary law arbitration in Nigeria.*

In Nigeria, there are chains and series of inconsistent and conflicting judicial pronouncements and decisions of courts on customary law arbitration. There exists also conflicting decisions on the validity of customary law arbitration and whether customary law arbitration by oath taking is valid and enforceable in Nigeria. It is to answer these questions and more that I have decided to undertake this research work.

Keywords: *Customary law arbitration, Arbitration, Oath taking arbitration, Validity of customary law arbitration, Dispute resolution, and Enforcement of Customary Law Arbitral Awards.*

1. Introduction

¹ Allot, *Essays in African Law*, Butterworth Co. Ltd., London, 1960, 126.

² (1988)4NWLR(Pt.90)544

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Before the enactment of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act Cap A18 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, and Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023, we had difference sources of the arbitration law. Nigerian arbitration law prior to 1988 was contained almost entirely in the customary law, common law and subsequently in Cap 13 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 1958. We have domestic and international arbitration. These two could be ad hoc or institutional. As stated above, we have customary law arbitration, common law arbitration and arbitration under the Act. In this paper, it is intended to discuss customary law arbitration with particular emphasis on the validity and enforceability of arbitral awards based on oath taking. How valid is arbitral awards based on oath taking? This paper intends to answer this question.

What is arbitration? According to Fulton Maxwell.J.

*Arbitration is a process whereby a private disinterested person called arbitrator, chosen by the parties to a dispute...acting in a judicial fashion but without regards to legal technicalities applying either existing law or norms agreed by the parties and acting in accordance with equity, good conscience and the perceived merit of the dispute makes an award to resolve the dispute.*³

Arbitration is an alternative dispute resolution method. According to the Supreme Court in *NNPC v. Lutin Investment Ltd*⁴ arbitration is the reference of a dispute or difference between not less than two parties for determination, after hearing both sides in a judicial manner, by a person other than a court of competent jurisdiction. On the other hand, customary law arbitration has been defined by the Supreme Court in *Agu v. Ikewibe*⁵ “as arbitration founded on the voluntary submission of the parties to the decision of the arbitrators who are either chiefs or elders of their communities and the agreement to be bounded by such decision...”

It is a reference to the decision of one or more persons either with or without an umpire of a particular matter in difference between the parties.⁶ Customary law arbitration agreement is oral as it is not required to be in writing. Even when the resultant arbitral award of customary arbitration agreement is reduced into writing, the arbitration is nonetheless customary law arbitration. It has to be emphasized that customary law arbitration exists in Nigerian communities before the court institutions and the advent of the colonial era. It was the most common and universally accepted mode of settlement of disputes in the hinterland. It was part of the culture and tradition of the Nigerian people and society. It was well organized and administered by the elders, chiefs, age grade groups, and ‘Umu ada’ (women league). The applicable laws in customary law arbitration are the

³ Fulton Maxwell J, *Commercial Alternative Dispute Resolution*, The Law Book Co. Ltd. 1989, 55.

⁴ (2006)NSCQR 77 at 111 -112. Halsburys Laws of England 3rd Ed. Vol.2 Para 2. 2.

⁵ *Agu v. Ikewibe* (1991)3 NWLR (Pt. 180)385 at 407.

⁶ Gaius Ezejiolor, (Pre-requisites of Customary Arbitration”, *Journal of Private and Property Law*, Vol.16, 34. Prof Greg C.Nwakoby, Customary Law Arbitration Practice, *Capital Bar Journal*, Awka Branch, Anambra State, 2010, 143.

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customs and tradition which guide and regulate the day to day activities of the people of Nigeria. The arbitration as stated above is based on the voluntary submission of the parties who are also members of the community.⁷

It is generally acknowledged that one of the many African mode of settlement of disputes is to refer it to the family head or even elders of the community for compromised solution based in the subsequent acceptance by both parties of the suggested award, which becomes binding only after such signification of its acceptance, and which either party is free to resile at any stage of the proceedings.⁸ In *Utomba v. Ahuchaogu*,⁹ Niki Tobi JSC (of late memory) gave a detailed definition of customary law arbitration. He defined it as a native arrangement by selected elders of the community who are vast in the customary law of the people and take decisions which are mainly designed and aimed at bringing some amicable settlement, harmony, stability and social equilibrium to the immediate society or environment.

In customary law arbitration, a neutral third party is requested by the parties or communities to settle dispute(s) for them adopting the custom and tradition applicable to them as the rules for the settlement. The people or persons often requested or required to settle disputes in the communities are the family head, kindred head, chiefs, elders, age grade groups where they exist, village council, traditional rulers, priests of shrines, league of daughters of the family (umu ada), trade associations, etc.¹⁰

Customary law arbitration is not something new to the indigenous people of Nigeria as it is enshrined in their custom and tradition. The custom of the Nigeria people is the engine and vehicle of the customary law arbitration. The custom is generally applicable unless it is contrary to public policy or repugnant to natural justice, equity and good conscience. Customary law arbitration which is derived from the custom and tradition of the people is recognized under the Nigerian legal system and by the Nigerian courts. The valid status of customary law arbitration has been given further impetus by the validity of customary law as a source of law in Nigeria. The importance of customary law is based on its usage or practice of the people which by common adoption and acquiescence and by long and unvarying habit has become compulsory and has acquired the force of law with respect to the place or

⁷ *Okereke v. Nwankwo* (2003)9 NWLR (Pt.626)592. *Agu v. Ikewibe*(1991)3 NWLR (Pt.180)385. M. M. Akanbi, A Critical Assessment of the History and Law of Domestic Arbitration in Nigeria: Trends in Nigeria Law", in Oluduro eta (eds.) Essays in Honour of Oba D. V. F. Olateru Ologbeji 111 Olowo of Owo Kingdom, Constellation Nig. Publishers, 462. Nwakoby Greg C, "Customary Law Arbitration Practice: Validity of Arbitration Award Based on Oath Taking", *Capital Bar Journal*, NBA, Awka Branch, July 2010, 142 at 143.

⁸ *Okereke v. Nwankwo*(2003)9NWLR(Pt.626)592. *Agu v. Ikewibe* (1993)3 NWLR(Pt.180)385. T. O. Elias, *The Nature of African Customary Law*, Manchester University Press, 1956, 513.

⁹⁹⁹⁹ (2003)8NWLR(Pt.821). Roland Otaru & Isaac Oluwole Agbede, Customary Arbitration in Nigeria Communities: The Genesis Through Case Law", *Caleb University International Journal of Law & Policy*, Vol.2, 2023, 113.

¹⁰ Roland Otaru & Isaac Oluwole Agdede, " Customary Arbitration in Nigeria Communities: The Genesis Through Case Law", 114.

the subject matter to which it relates.¹¹ The practice of arbitration according to earlier scholars, comes so to speak, naturally to primitive bodies of law, and after courts have been established by the State and a recourse to them has become the natural method of settling disputes, the practice continues because the parties to a dispute want to settle them with less formality and expense than is involved in a recourse to the court.¹²

2. The Existence and Legal Basis of Customary Law Arbitration.

As stated hereinbefore, customary law arbitration has suffered so many blows and attacks by scholars and jurists. Prominent among the attackers of the customary law arbitration in Nigeria are Uwaifo JCA and Allot. Sequel to these attacks leveled against customary law arbitration of the Nigeria people by Uwaifo JCA in *Okpuruwu v. Okpkam*¹³ and Allot in his book, *Essays in African Law*, one is only but put on enquiry as to whether customary law arbitration exists in fact. Uwaifo JCA (as he then was) had in *Okpuruwu v. Okpokam*¹⁴ expressed the view that “there is no concept known as customary or native arbitration in our jurisprudence.” With the greatest humility and respect, I submit that uwaifo JCA was in serious error. His statement on the matter was highly unsatisfactory and Oguntade’s opinion represented the correct position of the law. Oguntade JCA who dissented from the leading judgment delivered by Uwaifo JCA presented the correct position of the law when he stated thus:

*I find myself unable to accept the proposition that there is no concept known as customary or native arbitration in our jurisprudence. The regular courts in the early stages were reluctant to accord recognition to the decisions or awards of arbitration ... if parties to a dispute voluntarily submit their dispute to a third party as arbitrator and agreed to be bound by the decision of such arbitration then the court must clot such decision with the garb of estoppel per rem judicatam. I do not share the view that natives in their own communities cannot have custom which operate on the same basis of voluntary submission. The right to freely choose an arbitrator to adjudicate with binding effect is not one beyond our native communities.*¹⁵

The practice of chiefs and elders of the communities setting dispute among members of their communities is recognized by the Nigeria legal system and this practice has over the years become so strongly embedded in the system that they survive today as part of our customary law.¹⁶ It is submitted that customary law arbitration is part of our customary law and the practice of settlement of dispute in the communities by the elders is not one above the intelligence of Nigerian communities

¹¹ *Oyewumi v. Ogunesan* (1990)3 NWLR(Pt.137)182 at 207. *Aku v. Aneku* (1991)3NWLR (Pt.209)280 at 292.

¹² Williams Holdsworth. *History of English Law*, Vol. 14, 1964,187. F D. Emerson, “History of Arbitration Practice and Law”, *Cir St. Law Review*, 1970, 155.

¹³ *Okpuruwu v. Okpokam* (1988)4NWLR (Pt.90) 544.

¹⁴ *ibidi*

¹⁵ *ibidi*

¹⁶ *Agu v. Ikewibe(supra)*385. *Okere v. Nwoke*(1991)8NWLR(Pt.209)at 323.

and their people. Customary arbitration does not exist in isolation, it relies on the native custom and tradition of the people. It seems relatively obvious that His Lordship (Uwaifo JCA) took account of *Inyang v. Essein*¹⁷ in reaching his decision and conclusion in the matter of *Okpuruwu v. Okpokam*.¹⁸ On the other hand, Allot who unfortunately viewed customary law arbitration in Nigeria with tainted glass and jaundiced lens concluded that “the so called arbitration practice of the Nigeria people is a mere negotiation of settlement”.¹⁹ He criticized the dichotomization of the customary law dispute settlement process into arbitration and attempt at a negotiation for settlement as nonexistent. For him, the so called arbitration practice of the Nigerian people is a mere negotiation for settlement and the parties thereto are always free to resile from the arrangement at any time before the award is made. With respect, Allot was wrong in his assertion for there is a great difference between customary law arbitration and negotiation for settlement. In Nigeria, customary law arbitration exists independent of mere negotiation for settlement. For there to be customary law arbitration, the parties must have an agreement to go into the business of arbitration. In negotiation for settlement, the parties need not agree to embark on settlement of the dispute. Friends of the parties could on their own volition commence settlement moves and invite the parties. Customary law arbitration award binds the parties and is a form of judgment when declared valid and recognized by the court. On the other hand, the terms of negotiation for settlement does not bind the parties until such settlement term are accepted by the parties.²⁰

The legal basis of all arbitration practice including customary arbitration is voluntary agreement. If there is a distinct agreement to appoint an umpire to determine the difference between the parties and other conditions are present then there is arbitration. It is the arbitration agreement entered into by the parties that confers jurisdiction on the arbitral tribunal to undertake the arbitration. This element of voluntary nature of the agreement of the parties to submit a case or dispute for arbitration had been behind our concept of arbitration under customary law from the beginning. In *Foli v. Akese*²¹, Dean, CJ cited with approval the opinion of Marle . J in *Fuller Vs Fenwick* wherein he stated that,

If this case had gone in the usual course, the law would have been determined by a jury. The parties have thought fit that arbitration was more proper to decide matter of fact than a jury and could more conveniently dispose of matters of law than a judge on account of expense of contesting before

¹⁷ (1957)FSC 39

¹⁸ *Ibidi*.

¹⁹ Allot, *Essays in African Law*, Butterworth Co. Ltd. London, 1960, 126

²⁰ *Chidi Ekwueme v. Sani Zakari* (1972)2ECSLR 631.

²¹ (1930)1WACA1

*a court an intricate point of law.*²²

Where matters in dispute between the parties are by mutual consent investigated by arbitration at a meeting held in accordance with native law, a decision given, is binding on the parties, and the court will enforce it. This has the support of the Supreme Court of Nigeria in *Egesimba v. Onuzurike*²³ where the court stated thus;

customary arbitration by elders of the community is one of many African customary modes of settling dispute and once it satisfies the necessary requirements the decision would have binding effect on the parties and this creates an estoppel. It is recognized under Nigeria jurisprudence.

The Supreme Court of Nigeria has in so many cases maintained and emphasized recognition of arbitration based on customary law of the Nigerian people. In *Odonigi v. Oyeleke*, the court held that the decision of the Court of Appeal in *Okpuruwu v. Okpokam* that Nigerian legal system does not recognize the practice of elders, chiefs or natives constituting themselves as customary arbitration to make binding decisions between parties in respect of land or other disputes cannot be correct.²⁴ Sequel to the decision of Uwaifo JCA in *Okpuruwu v. Okpokam*,²⁵ the counsel to the appellant in *Agu v. Ikwibe*²⁶ argued and urged the court to hold that customary law arbitration is unknown to Nigerian law. That the Nigerian law did not recognize the practice of elders and natives as customary arbitration to make binding decisions between the parties in respect of land or other disputes. He went further to state that customary law arbitration is contrary to section 6(1) and 5 of the 1979 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, now section 6 of the 1999 Constitution as amended. The Supreme Court per Karibi-Whyte JSC held that despite the judicial powers of the Constitution in section 6 (1) and section 6(5) vested in the courts named in that section, it does not prevent disputing parties from settling their differences in a manner acceptable to them. The court went further and stated that customary law arbitration is not an exercise of the judicial power of the Constitution, since it is not a function undertaken by the courts.²⁷

It is necessary and important to mention at this juncture that customary law is by virtue of section 274(3) and (4)(b) of the 1979 Constitution an existing law by virtue of the fact that it is a body of an existing law before the coming into force of the Constitution. It was part of the law saved by the Constitution. Customary law arbitration which is an aspect of the customary law of Nigerian people was saved by the provisions of section 274(3) and (4) of the 1979 Constitution. His Lordship in his

²² (1846)161 J.C.P. 79.

²³ (2002)15 NWLR (Pt.79)466 at 512.

²⁴ *Odonigi v. Oyeleke* (2001)FWLR(Pt.42)172 at 190-191.

²⁵ *ibidi*

²⁶ *ibidi*

²⁷ *ibidi*.

words stated that, “I think it is well settled and judicial authority is not lacking for the view that persons exercising judicial functions in accordance with native law and custom and who are dully authorized to adjudicate among their community have always been recongnised as having such powers. The provisions of the Constitution of 1979, sections 6(1) and (5) have not altered the judicial position.”²⁸ It is worthy of note that section 274(3 and (4) of the 1979 Constitution has now been replaced by section 315(1) and (3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which also corroborated and supported this view.²⁹

3. How to Plead and Prove the Existence of Customary Law Arbitration

As hereinbefore stated, customary law arbitration agreement is oral and as such there is bound to be issue of conflicting or divergent evidence of its existence. Customary law arbitration agreement is oral and its resultant arbitral award is also not required to be in writing. As the award is oral, there is likelihood of conflict of evidence of its contents and in whose favour it was made. The law is that where there is conflict of evidence of the content of a customary law arbitral award, the court must undertake a fact finding mission and this can only be done by calling of oral evidence. The court is duty bound to admit evidence of the parties and weigh same on that imaginary scale as stated by the Supreme Court in *Idika v. Erisi*³⁰ wherein the court stated thus:

It is settled law that where there is divergent evidence of customary law arbitration, the court could make a specific finding of fact whether there was properly constituted arbitration since the arbitration would be binding on the parties. The decision arrived at is of particular importance in enabling the court to arrive at a just decision.

This was also affirmed by Oguntade JCA in *Okere V Nwoke*¹⁵, Where he stated thus, *With respect to the learned judge, I cannot accept the simplistic treatment he gave this issue. He made no attempt whatsoever, to put the case of each party on imaginary scale as strongly suggested by the Supreme Court in Mogaji vs Odofin. It is not enough to say, I do not believe the plaintiffs, I prefer it (defendant’s story).*

From the foregoing, the court has an important duty to evaluate the evidence of the parties before enforcing a customary law award which is only enforceable by action at law.

The next question is, what is the successful party in the arbitration required by law to plead in his pleading before the court and what is he required to prove? Though the issue of the existence of customary law arbitration is now settled, there are certain criteria that must be met before the arbitral award of customary law arbitration is declared valid and enforced. It is most unfortunate and disturbing that despite the compulsory validity of customary arbitration by courts of law, there are no

²⁸ *Ibidi*.

²⁹ Roland Otaru & Isaac Oluwole Agbede, “Customary Arbitration in Nigerian Communities: The Genesis Through Case Law” 119

³⁰ (1988)2NWLR (Pt)78)562 at 572.

uniform criteria for its validity. In *Okoye v. Obiaso*,³¹ the court decided that a party can prove the existence of a customary arbitration by pleading and establishing the following:

- (a) there has been a voluntary submission of the matter in dispute to an arbitration of one or more persons;
- (b) It was agreed by the parties either expressly or by implication, that the decision of the arbitration will be accepted as final and binding;
- (c) The said arbitration was in accordance with the custom of the parties or their trade or business;
- (d) The arbitrators reached a decision and published their award;
- (e) The award was accepted at the time it was made.

These criteria were reiterated by the court in *Awonusi v. Awonusi*.³² The Supreme Court had in *Agu v ikewible*³³, and *Ohiaeri v Akabueze*³⁴ decided that the plaintiff would succeed if he is able to prove:-

1. That the dispute between the parties was deliberated upon by a third party;
2. That the third party gave a decision in his favor;
3. That a valid customary arbitration exists where the party voluntarily submitted to the arbitration;
4. That the parties agreed beforehand to be bound by the arbitral decision;
5. That none of the parties withdrew from the arbitration midstream.
6. That none of the parties rejected the award immediately it was made;
7. And that the arbitrators reached a decision and published their award.

In *Egesimba v Onuzurike*³⁵ the Supreme Court of Nigeria at one arm stated that the plaintiff has duty to plead and prove the following:-

- a. voluntary submission of the dispute to the arbitration of the individual body;
- b. agreement by the parties either expressly or implication that the decision of the arbitration will be accepted as binding;
- c. that the arbitration was in accordance with the custom of the parties And
- d. that the arbitration reached a decision and published his award.

Going further, Supreme Court extended its decision to also include the following,

- a. that the parties voluntarily submitted their dispute to a non-judicial body, to wit their elders or chiefs as the case may be for determination; and
- b. the indication of the willingness of the parties to be bound by the decision of the judicial body

³¹ (2010)JELR43027.

³² (2007)33 WRN 43 at 52-53.

³³ *ibidi*

³⁴ *ibidi*

³⁵ *Egesimba v Onuzurike (supra)*406 at 505

or freedom to reject the decision where not satisfied;

c. that neither of the parties has resiled from the decision where not satisfied.³⁶

Uwaifo JSC in *Eke v. Okwaranyia*³⁷ held that anything short of these conditions will make any customary arbitration award risky to enforce. It is better to say that unless these conditions are fulfilled and met the arbitration award is unenforceable.

With respect, the decisions of the Supreme Court in the cases referred above were unsatisfactory. The reasons for my position are supported by earlier decisions of courts and the principles of guiding the customary law of the Nigeria people. A party to the arbitration agreement cannot reject the award made by the arbitration following the submission made to him because the award is not favorable to him. In *Foli v Akese*³⁸ Deane J., stated that “in submission to arbitration, the general rule is that as the parties choose their arbitrator to be judge in dispute between them, they cannot when the award is good on its face object to his decision either upon the law or on the facts.” A party who has consented to arbitration under the customary law cannot also resile from the proceedings midstream or after an award is made unless he can show in evidence that such a right so to resile exists under his custom. This is because a party who had led another to take a particular step in proceeding would not be allowed to withdraw to the detriment of that other that had acted in good faith and in honest belief that both parties would be bound by the proceedings and the decision taken therein. According to professor Gaius Ezejiofor with whom I agreed, the preexisting law which required a party to keep faith with his promise is not without justification. If a party voluntary entered into an agreement with another to submit a dispute for settlement by a particular person(s) and to accept the decision of such tribunal or person, he has a moral and just obligation not to frustrate the process by withdrawing midstream or rejecting the decision when it does not favor him. Consequently, the doctrine, *interest rei publicae ut sit finis litium* is very fundamental and is recognized and applied by all courts.³⁹ The Privy Council in affirming this proposition had this to say:-

*Since it is established that the parties gave their consent to the submission of the dispute to elders without any express reservation of right to resile and since there is certainly no right to resile after award is made, it is for the appellant to satisfy the boards that a right so contrary to the basic conception of arbitration is recognized by native customary law*⁴⁰

The Supreme Court held in *Oparaji v. Ohanu* per Igu JSC that;

³⁶ *Egesimba v. Onuzurike (supra)* 406 at 511.

³⁷ (2001)86 LRCN 1403.

³⁸ *Foli v. Akese (supra)* 1

³⁹ Prof. Gaius Ezejiofor, “The Pre requisite of Customary Arbitration”, *Journal of Private and Property Law*, Vol.16, 34. Greg ChukwudiNwakoby, *The Law and Practice of Commercial Arbitration in Nigeria*, 3rd Ed. 2014, 116 -119.

⁴⁰ *Kwasi & Ors v. Larbi* 13WACA 76 at 80.

I think I ought to start by restating the well settled principle of law that where two parties to a dispute voluntarily submit the issue in controversy between them to an arbitration in customary law and agreed expressly or by implication that the decision of such arbitration would be accepted as final and binding, then once the arbitrators reach a decision, it would no longer be open to either of the parties to subsequently back out or resile from the decision so pronounced.⁴¹

The law is that in every arbitration agreement, there is an implied undertaking by the parties that an award made shall bind the parties.⁴² In the circumstance, there is no need to require the successful party to arbitration to plead and prove that such express or implied undertaking to be bound by the award exists. This is because the law already implied that the duty to perform the term of an agreement or contract exists. The requirement to prove that all the parties accepted the award when made by the tribunal sounds so ludicrous and funny. Who will voluntarily accept a decision which turns against him? This is not the requirement of the law. An award once made becomes effective and binding. The only remedy open to an unsatisfied party is to apply to court to have the award set aside or impeached. The duty of an arbitrator is to make a good arbitral award and publish same to the parties. The issue of whether the parties accepted the award when made is strange and unsatisfactory. It is not part of our jurisprudence.

In general, the decisions in *Agu v ikewibe*⁴³ and *Ohiaeri v Akabueze*⁴⁴ do not adequately represent the correct position of the law. However the decision in *Egesimba v. Onuzurike*⁴⁵ represented the correct position of the law in part. The court derailed when it added yet addition three elements to be proved then making them seven as in previous other decisions of the Supreme Court. It was this additional ground that made the decision unsatisfactory. With respect and humility, the three elements which the plaintiff ought to plead and prove are:

- a. Voluntary submission of the dispute to the arbitration of the individual or body in accordance with the agreement of the parties;
- b. Arbitration in accordance with the customary law of the parties.
- c. That an award was made and published to the parties.

It has to be stated that the Supreme Court of Nigeria decisions in *Agu v. Ikewibe* and *Ohieri v Akabueze* are the superior decisions on the matter of validity and provisions for requirement for recognition and enforcement of customary arbitral award in Nigeria. The decisions in the two cases and also in *Ohiaeri v. Akabueze* remain the basic requirement for validity and enforcement of

⁴¹ (1999)9NWLR(Pt.618) 290 at 304.

⁴² *Charles Ume v. Godrey S A Okoronkwo & Anor* (1996)2 SCNJ 404.

⁴³ *ibidi*

⁴⁴ *ibidi*

⁴⁵ *Egesimba v. Onuzurike* (supra) 406 at 505

customary arbitral award in Nigeria. Any award which fails to meet any of these seven requirements as set out by the Supreme Court of Nigeria will not be enforceable. This is most unfortunate but it remains the law. I do strongly recommend a reversal of the requirements in future decisions of the Supreme Court. I will also consider each of these seven elements so as to buttress their implications in the law.

(a) Voluntary Submission of dispute to arbitration - The first arm of the requirement is that the parties must have voluntarily submitted their dispute to the arbitrators who are their elders or chiefs. This element of voluntary submission of dispute to arbitration on the agreement of the parties is not monopoly of customary law arbitration but of all arbitration including arbitration under the Act and common law arbitration. When we consider the commencement of customary law arbitration, it may seem that there is often no voluntary agreement to arbitrate. The reason being that, under the native law and custom, customary law arbitration begins when there is dispute between two or more parties, and one of them decides to report the issue to the elders in the family or kindred. The other party who is reported will often be 'summoned' to the tribunal, and in most cases the other party has no choice but to appear before the arbitral tribunal.⁴⁶ The question which scholars have asked is whether "summoned" as used herein amount to voluntary submission? Are parties at liberty to reject the summons and refuse to appear before the elder(s) and would the party who refused, be subjected to any form of punishment by the family or community? The Supreme Court of Nigeria in *Agu v. Ikwibe* decided thus;

Now the word summoned as used ... the essence of summons is to command. So when the respondent pleaded that he summoned the appellant before the chiefs and elders of the two who gave judgment in favour of the plaintiff, I clearly understand it to mean that the appellant was bound to appear before them whether he liked it or not and whether or not he wanted them to go into the dispute between them. This is clearly antithetic to voluntary submission which is of the very essence of a valid arbitration agreement. It must be borne in mind that arbitrators are not a court. They are not clothed by the Constitution with any judicial authority as such. It is the High court of a State which has unlimited jurisdiction under section 236 of the 1979 Constitution to adjudicate on all civil and criminal matters relating to legal rights, obligations, powers, and duty, interest, privilege or claim, penalty, forfeiture, punishment or other liability... On the other hand, arbitration bodies have no such powers. The binding effect of their decisions derives from the fact that parties which have the right to resort to court for adjudication of their disputes have, with their eyes wide open, agree to opt for a decision by a non-judicial body, the decision of which they have voluntarily agreed to be bound by. When a party to such a dispute has to be summoned before the arbitration

⁴⁶ Roland Otaru & Isaac Oluwole Agbede, "Customary Arbitration in Nigerian Communities: The Genesis Through Case Law" 123.

*body which proceeds to hear the dispute and thereafter pass a judgment in favour of one of the parties as if it were a judicial body, such cannot be said to be a valid arbitration. The element of voluntary submission which is of the very essence of arbitration according to custom is lacking.*⁴⁷

It is a known fact that it is not always that the disputing parties must always meet and agree to submit their differences or disputes to elders or chiefs. To use the word summoned in customary law arbitration is unfair to the custom and tradition of the Nigerian communities. This is because the elders or chiefs do not summon anyone but rather invite the other party to appear and be heard so as to ascertain the truth of the matter. The essence of customary law arbitration is not so much for a party to win than to establish harmony and stability in the community. The elders do not summon parties but invite them. The voluntary nature of the respondent would be seen in his attitude when he appears before the elders. In some places, the complainant who complained to the elders may be required to establish his complaint with a keg of palm wine or some kola nuts as the case may be, whereas the respondent against whom the claim is brought may also be required to present similar number of kola nuts if he wants the elders or chiefs to wade into the matter. The elders or chiefs have no instrument of compelling any party to appear before them. The requirement of voluntary submission varies from community to community. The usual practice is that one party makes a complaint to the elders or chiefs, the other party is invited or sent for, and if he accepts, the person(s) to whom the complaint is made to, arbitrate upon the dispute for them.

Voluntary submission is one of the cardinal rules and principle in arbitration practice generally. The resultant award in arbitration will definitely not be enforced if evidence exists that the parties did not voluntarily submitted to arbitration. This could be seen in *Chidi Ekwueme v. Sani Zakari*⁴⁸ where the two parties were in hotel partnership business at Abakaliki. When they had dispute, their five mutual friends waded into the matter with intent to settle for them. At the end of the settlement process, they awarded some amount of money to the plaintiff. The plaintiff sought to enforce the decision of their five mutual friends but the High court upon finding that there was no voluntary agreement by the parties before the decision was reached declined to enforce the decision as an award as there was no agreement between the parties to refer their matter to arbitration. What went on in the matter can at best be said to be an attempt at settlement or negotiation for settlement but certainly not arbitration by any standard.

(b) Acceptance of the Award when made and none of the parties resile mid-stream- It is a requirement that the award must be accepted by the parties when same was made by the arbitrator(s). This sounds very funny. Who on earth will voluntarily and willingly accepted a decision that is against

⁴⁷ (1991)3 NWLR (Pt.180)385.

⁴⁸ (1972)2ECSLR 631. Greg C. Nwakoby, *The Law and Practice of Commercial Arbitration in Nigeria*, 2014, 20.

him? It is enough if the arbitrator(s) reached an award and published same to the parties. It should not be the concern of either party or the arbitrator if or not a party accepted or rejected the decision. A party who is not satisfied by the award should ordinarily approach the court to set aside the award for good reason. This principle applies to other forms of arbitration and one then wonders why this element should be imported into the jurisprudence of the Nigerian people. On the requirement of proving that none of the parties withdrew midstream before the award was made. It is even unconscionable for a party to abandon the proceedings after agreeing with his fellow to go on arbitration. The court should not allow this practice or encourage it. Once a party accepted and agreed to go into arbitration with his fellow, it is only fair that he should keep faith with the process on the principle of *pacta sunct suvander*. The same argument goes for the right of party to resile midstream into the arbitration. A party who has entered into an arbitration agreement with his fellow should not have the right to withdraw midstream into the arbitration. Exercise of such right will impact negatively on customary law arbitration in Nigeria. The right to reject an arbitral award or resile on the basis of being dissatisfied with the proceedings or the resultant award should not be taken the way some courts have decided it. When one is dissatisfied with an award, the law gives the person the opportunity of impeaching the award using the right instrument of the law. The right to resile is totally out of it. This explains why the court in *George Onwusike v. Patrick Onwusike*⁴⁹ decided thus; *The decision given by the elders, authorized by custom to settle such disputes, and exercising their customary functions, as a result of the submission of the parties to their jurisdiction, unless clearly wrong in principle, is binding on them... I apprehend that it would be contrary to common sense to allow persons who have voluntarily submitted their dispute to an independent body of their own choosing to render nugatory the decision arrived at, merely because it does not favour the interest they assert or in some other way is regarded by them as unsatisfactory.*

(c) The award was published to the parties when it was made. The publication of the arbitral award to the parties in the customary law arbitration is not same with that of the magistrate or High court where the judgment is required to be written and read to the parties in the open court by the judge. In customary law arbitration, an award is said to be published when the decision of the elders or chiefs are pronounced orally at the meeting convened for arbitration. The award is not required to be in writing. As stated earlier, the arbitration agreement under the customary law is oral and even if the arbitral award is reduced into writing, it is nonetheless customary arbitration. In this age and time when most of the elders and chiefs are well educated, it is not surprising to have the award reduced into writing and handed to the parties. Where the arbitrator(s) reduces the award into writing, it will be appreciated but that is not the requirement of the customary law arbitration.

⁴⁹ (1926)6 Eastern Nigeria Law Report 1

4. Customary Law Arbitration Award Based on Oath Taking

Oath taking is an accepted practice under the customary law and is a common feature of resolving dispute in Africa. It was frequently adopted in the settlement of land matter in the hinterland. In *Charles Ume v Godfrey A Okoronkwo & Anor*,⁵⁰ there was a native arbitration in respect of titles to land in dispute. The plaintiff was adjudged the owner of the land. In course of proceedings, the first defendant claimed that the 2nd defendant was his caretaker over the land. The plaintiff was required to swear on a juju to be produced by the first defendant. The first defendant failed to produce the juju”. Thereafter the plaintiff resumed possession of the land and farmed it. Delivering the lead judgment Oguegbu, J.S.C stated thus, *Oath taking was one of the methods of establishing the truth of a matter and was known to customary law and accepted by both parties. The defendant only resiled after the arbitration had made their awards by refusing to produce the ‘juju’. It was not open to him to do so at that stage.*⁵¹

One thing that is obvious is the fact that oath taking is an acceptable feature of customary law but what is striking and certain in this case was that oath was not even taken by either party to the suit. This being the situation, this case cannot serve the purpose of our discussion. However, in *Ofomate & Ors v. Anoka*, Agbokoba J. held that; *Oath taking is however a recognized and accepted form of proof existing in certain customary judicature, oath may be sworn extra judicial but as a mode of Judicial proof its esoteric and reverential feature, the solemnity of the choice of oath by the disputants and imminent evil visitation to oath breaker, if he swore falsely, are the deterrent sanctions of this form of customary Judicial process which commends it alike to rural and urban indigenous courts. It is therefore my view that the decision to swear an oath is not illegal although it may be obnoxious to Christian ethics; Christianity, however, has not come to destroy, its mission is to deify, to correct and reconcile.*⁵²

In the most recent case of *Umeadi v. Chibunze*, the Supreme Court of Nigeria decided that where parties who believe in the efficacy of juju, resort to oath – taking to settle a dispute, they are bound by the result and so the common law principle in respect of proof of title to land no longer applies since the proof of ownership of title to land will be based on the rules set out by that traditional arbitration resulting in oath taking.⁵³ In *Onyenge & Ors v. Ebere*, the Supreme Court further affirmed the practice of oath taking in customary arbitration wherein the court stated thus;-

Oath taking is a valid process under customary law arbitration and it is one of the methods known

⁵⁰ (1996)12 SCNJ 404.

⁵¹ *ibidi*

⁵² (1974)4 ECLSR 51

⁵³ (2020)10 NWLR (Pt.1733)405.

*to customary law for establishing the truth of a matter where two parties to a dispute voluntarily agreed to the resolution of their dispute by oath taking in accordance with customary law, neither of them can thereafter resile from the exercise of oath taking.*⁵⁴

It is actually an established fact that oath taking is part of our customary law arbitration practice but the relevant question which the court have not answered is the certainty of the practice in terms of efficacy of the oath or the juju used in the exercise. As in the instant case, the first shrine was rejected by the respondents for obvious reasons of uncertainty and bias on the part of the juju priest. Even the efficacy of the second juju which was used was not verified by anybody as there exists no instrument for testing same. We must agree as it is widely known that oath taking involves spiritually and the minor gods or deities. It is wrong to leave the determination of issues of rights, obligations, duties and interests of citizens in the unseen hands of the gods and deities.

As stated earlier in this work, it is not in doubt that under the native law of Nigerian people, parties in certain circumstance consent to oath taking as the means of settling their dispute. In such circumstance, time is usually given within which the offending party is expected to either be killed by the gods or be sick so as to confirm that he is the offending party. If after the time given for the offending party to die and he fails to die, the other party would not be allowed by the court to resile from the settlement and re open the matter. In *Okere v Nwoke*⁵⁵, the respondent admitted the custom of settling dispute by oath taking. The appellants having been led to take oath on the "Aka Obibi juju" provided by the 3rd defendant at great risk to their lives in the belief that the customary oath would settle the dispute, the respondent are estopped by conduct from denying that appellants were thereby adjudged owners of the land, the latter having sworn the oath for over a year.

With humility and respect to the learned jurist in *Okere V Nwoke*⁵⁶, I strongly disagree with this ancient and outdated practice of oath taking as an acceptable customary law arbitration practice. The practice is not only obnoxious, uncivilized, outdated, and anachronistic but also barbaric and uncertain. In *Iwuchukwu v. Anyanwu*⁵⁷ Ndoma Egba, JCA. captured the situation very well wherein he started thus;

The believe of the learned tried judge that dispute are decided by swearing "juju" may be true as a matter of past. In this century, that will be a retreat to trial by ordeal which is unthinkable any more than swearing "juju" as a method of proof. We cannot now reel back to superstitious fear for sake our religious faith.

One of the principal features of an arbitration award is that the award must be final and must not be

⁵⁴ (2004)13 NWLR (Pt.889)20 at 24.

⁵⁵ (1999)8NWLR(Pt209)344

⁵⁶ *Ibidi*.

⁵⁷ (1993) NWLR(Pt.311)307 at 323.

contingent or conditional. An arbitral award based on oath taking is not a final award. It is a conditional award as the award becomes effective and final after the time given in the oath taking has elapsed. In this circumstance the customary arbitral award based on oath taking is not final as the finality of it depends on the outcome of the oath or its resultant effect. Its finality is dependent on the happening of an event.

At the times of taking of oath under the customary law, the medical condition and state of health of the “oath taker” is not often ascertained and in which case, his or her state of health is unknown. Is it that any form of death after taking of oath suffices? It often happened that when a man after taking oath dies in an aircraft crash, fatal road accident, cancer, prostate problem, malaria, etc it is taken that the oath had killed him. What is the form of death that results from the oath taking? The form of death resulting from oath taking is uncertain and unknown.

Oath taking involves unnecessary superstition, mystery, divination, and spirituality. In our jurisprudence, superstition and spiritually are not recognized. They are not accorded any legal force or recognition. In oath taking, one is dealing with spiritual force, deities and gods. These are unseen forces whose existence is based on mere faith and belief. The court had in *Onwuanukpa v. Onwuaunkpa*⁵⁸ condemned this practice as not being arbitration.

There is no test of efficacy of the oath being taken. There have been cases of manipulation of the oath by the chief priest or even elders. There are situations wherein the antidote of a particular oath is known to some elders and natives. In such cases, adverse claimants may enter into another person’s land and immediately thereafter submit himself (themselves) to oath taking knowing full well that the antidote of the oath exists. No doubt, oath taking is a form of trial by ordeal which is both criminal and illegal. Custom as we know it is dynamic and not static. Based on the current level of sophistication in our customary law and our communities, it will be repugnant to natural justice, equity and good conscience to still continue with this ancient practice which is fetish, barbaric, uncivilized, outdated, uncertain, and anachronistic. It is my candid opinion that our courts should not recognize arbitration award based on oath taking as oath taking has a lot of uncertainties surrounding it called “ndagbu iyi” (antidote to oath taking). The antidotes to most oaths have been in existence for years and are known to some elders and natives in the villages. In the circumstance of these attacks against oath taking, one should take an award based on the same with a pinch of salt. It has been said that once parties agree to oath taking, they should be allowed to wallow in their ignorance. Some scholars have argued that in our courts, parties and witnesses take oath before giving their testimonies. It is true that witnesses swear to an oath before giving their testimony in court. The situations are not the same. The fact remains that the witness testimony in the court aids and assists

⁵⁸ (1993)8NWLR (Pt.310)186

the judge in the determination of the matter. It is not just the oath taken by witnesses that determine the case in the court. In court, cases are determined by the judge on the strength of the evidence adduced and not on the oath taken by witnesses. The judge has discretion to even disbelief a witness after the witness must have given his evidence on oath. In the customary law oath taking, it is the oath that decides the matter.

Constitutionally speaking, settlement of issues of rights, duties, and obligations in customary law arbitration through oath taking is unconstitutional. The reason for this is because section 36(1) of the 1999 Constitution provides that the determination of issues of rights and interest of the citizens shall be by courts, tribunal, and such other bodies as established by law. Which law established oath taking as a form of settlement of dispute in Nigeria? Oath taking is part of our customary law and since it is in contrast with the provisions of section 36(1) of the Constitution, it is then repugnant and should be declared invalid.

5. Enforcement of Customary Arbitral Award

The aim of the arbitrators, elders and the members of the community in customary law arbitration practice is not so much to impose a decision than to ensure peace and harmony within their community. Where a disputant or party against whom an award is made refuses to comply with the terms of the decision of the arbitration, the major aim of restoring harmony has not been achieved. The only sanction against the recalcitrant party in such circumstance in order to produce compliance and accept the elders ruling or the awards of the arbitrator will lie in the moral, social, and ritual position and authority of the elders or arbitrators backed by the weight of opinion in the family together with the threat of expulsion and excommunication from the group, or at least the withdrawal of support from the unsuccessful party on whom traditional fine may also be imposed by the members of the community. Where there is a high extra familiar authority within the community for example the title men association ('OZO'), age grade system, the woman association (umu ada), then these may be appealed to either by the successful party in the arbitration or, more frequent by the head of the family or elders who want backing for their award.

Often, the political authority will automatically accept and back up the decision or award where the award is fair and just. This traditional mode of enforcement of customary law arbitration awards in the traditional communities by way of excommunication of the unsuccessful party or by denial of certain rights within the community though recognized in practice may be counterproductive and lead to legal action in court. The excommunication of the unsuccessful party in the arbitration from the rest of the community may be interpreted to be an infringement of the fundamental human right of the person to peaceful assembly and association particularly if the person can prove that there are some people within the community who ordinarily intend and wish to associate with him but for the excommunication order against him. Secondly, this may lead to self-help practice in the community

where “traditional fine” is involved. In such a case, the members of the community may take it upon themselves to confiscate the property of the unsuccessfully party in which case criminal assault may result. Thirdly, it is not certain that even after the imposition of the “traditional fine” and excommunication, the unsuccessful party in the arbitration will perform the terms of the award. The unsuccessful party may still refuse to perform the terms of the award, in which case the desired harmony is equally not achieved. The arbitral tribunal whether constituted by the elders or by the age grade members has no authority whatsoever to enforce the award made by them. This is because the arbitral tribunal becomes *functus officio* upon making the award. A person who is not a party to the arbitration agreement has no right to enforce the award made in favour of another person hence it is contrary to law for the members of the community, the elders, or the age grade to enforce the award made by the elders. The law empowered the party in whose favor the award was made to file an action in court for the enforcement of the same.

The enforcement of the customary law arbitration award by this form of traditional method seems unsatisfactory, ineffective and highly unsuitable in the modern society when viewed against the premise that it may lead to hardship and law suit on issue which are not connected with the subject matter save and except for the mode of enforcement of customary arbitration award. Enforcement of customary law arbitration award by action at law in court of competent jurisdiction should be adhered to.

Action at law is the only recognized and accepted procedure for the enforcement of customary arbitral award. The traditional procedure is unacceptable. By action at law the successful party is required to commence his proceedings by issuance of writ and in which case the law requires him to lead evidence in support of the award made in his favour by customary arbitral tribunal. As to what he will be required to prove, the Supreme Court of Nigeria had in *Ohiaeri v. Akabueze*,⁵⁹ *Agu v. ikewibe*,⁶⁰ *Egesimba v. Onuzurike*⁶¹ set out what the successful party is expected to plead and prove.

Conclusion

Customary law arbitration practice is recognized as part of our customary law which is valid and still in practice not only in Nigeria but in Africa generally. Customary law arbitration is still being used and obeyed by many communities in Nigeria. It is most applied in cases of land disputes in the hinter land. Unfortunately, in Nigeria the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 made no reference or provision for the native or customary arbitration. However, in our Statutes Books and even in our Laws of Evidence particularly in section 66 of the Evidence Act 2011 provisions are made for the customary law which is the vehicle for customary arbitration. From the research, it is certain and obvious that customary law arbitration exists in Nigeria. There are certain conflicts as

⁵⁹ *Ohiaeri v. Akabueze (supra)*1

⁶⁰ *Agu v. Ikewibe (supra)*385

⁶¹ *Egesimba v. Onuzurike (supra)*466 at 513

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to the requirements for its validity but that could be said to have been resolved as the Supreme Court of Nigeria had in *Agu v. Ikewibe*, *Ohiaeri v. Akabueze*, and *Egesimba v. Onuzurike* laid the matter to rest. Oath taking arbitration is also recognized in Nigeria as a valid method of customary arbitration and its resultant awards are enforceable in our courts. There are three forms of enforcement procedure of customary arbitral awards in Nigeria namely; by imposition of traditional fine on the unsuccessful party so as to compel performance of the terms of the awards; the act of excommunication (ostracism) of the unsuccessful party from the rest of the communities so as to ensure compliance with the terms of the awards, and finally by action at law. It must be stated that though the first two are in practice, they are not recommended as they are contrary to law. The legally approved method of enforcement of customary arbitral award is by action at law.